

Framework for academic developers

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We invited participants to join us to explore a framework that describes academic development (AD) activities across multiple third space spectra, and to map their own projects in these spaces. Participants tested and explored the framework, considering how to use it in their own projects for planning, evaluation and impact.

The University of Melbourne Built Environments Learning and Teaching (BEL+T) Group is a faculty AD group. BEL+T operates in three forms: as a design studio, as a consultancy, and as a research group. These approaches cross three spectra in our framework: modes of operation (Academic and Professional); values and goals (Staff and Institutional); and planned outcomes and impact (Research and Teaching). This interactive workshop explored these spectra through mapping of participants' experiences, followed by reflection and discussion of the commonalities and differences uncovered through this activity.

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